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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

The Use of Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in the Development of Critical Thinking	16
<i>Gulnar Atakhanova Orinbaevna</i>	
Current Aspects of Designing and Implementing Extracurricular Educational Activities at the Primary General Education Level.....	20
<i>Amankosova Dinara Gabitovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida tarbiyachi shaxsiyati va kasbiy mahorati shakllanishining nazariy asoslari....	24
<i>Axmadaliyeva Moxlaroy To'xtapolatovna</i>	
Pedagogical Model and Stages of Teaching Subjects Through a Project-Based Approach	28
<i>Bannayev Qosimjon</i>	
Lotin tili va zamonaviy tibbiy terminologiya: tarixi, vazifasi va amaliy ahamiyati	31
<i>Eshmurodova Shirin Oybekovna</i>	
Motor alaliyaning nonutqiy simptomatikasi	34
<i>Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi</i>	
Talabalar etnomadaniy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari	38
<i>Isomiddinov Asliddin Baxriddin o'g'li</i>	
Texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarning texnik savodxonligini robototexnika elementlari asosida rivojlantirish.....	41
<i>Jabborova Umida</i>	
Fizika fanini mutaxassislik fanlari integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishda bo'lajak muhandislarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	45
<i>Xayrullayev Asliddin Isatullayevich</i>	
Talaba tomonidan mutaxassislik tilini o'zlashtirishda monologik nutqni o'rgatishning samarali usullari masalasi haqida.....	51
<i>Karimov N. M.</i>	
Zamonaviy pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda kasbiy motiv va motivatsiyaning o'rni	54
<i>Melikova Elnora Shuxratovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda pragmatik kompetensiyaning roli.....	58
<i>Mustafayeva Nilufar Ulashovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari	62
<i>Nishonova Dilafuz</i>	
Computer-Based Formative Assessment: Advantages and Challenges in Teaching English to High School Students	66
<i>Obidjonova Shokhista Bakhtiyorovna</i>	
Metata'lim texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	70
<i>O'rolboyeva Durdona Sayfiddin qizi</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi darslarning an'anaviy darslarga nisbatan samaradorligini qiyosiy tahlil qilish.....	73
<i>Rasulev Bobirjan Atxamovich</i>	
Pedagogik faoliyatda pedagogning kasbiy taraqqiyoti motivatsiyasining psixologik xususiyatlari	78
<i>Rustamova Surayyo Shaxobiddinovna</i>	
Innovatsion kompetentlik tushunchasi va uning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	84
<i>Soliyev Eliyor Ravshan o'g'li</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar eshituv idrokini o'yinlar yordamida rivojlantirishning samarali usullari	88
<i>Xalilova Shahnoza</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'limda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	92
<i>Yaqubova Nigoraxon Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Soliq yuki – mamlakat soliq soliq tizimining asosiy mezonidir	97
<i>Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish yo'llari	101
<i>Ibodova Sarvinoz Sayfilloyevna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida hospital pedagogika fanini o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari va uning uslubiy ta'minoti	106
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rahmatullaevna</i>	

Chizma geometriya va kompyuter grafikasi: an'anaviy fan va zamonaviy texnologiyaning uyg'unlashuvi .	111
<i>Raximov A. M., Tairova N. S., Sabirova D. U., Xasanova S. T., Tashpulatov R. X.</i>	
Геймификация в обучении английскому языку на начальном этапе обучения	114
<i>Курбанова Назира Низомиддиновна</i>	
Talabalarda tanqidiy va evristik fikrlashni shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni	117
<i>Adjdiyev Nayrullo Nazrulloevich</i>	
Konstruktiv yondashuv asosida tabiiy fanlar (science)ni o'qitish metodikasi.....	122
<i>Amirullayeva Barno Abdulhaqovna</i>	
Kimyo o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini shakllantirishning tajriba-sinov natijalari.....	126
<i>Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarni bilingvist sifatida shakllantirishda til o'rganish ko'nikmalari va kompetentsiyalarining rivojlanishi	131
<i>Axmadjonova Gulira'no Muxtorjon qizi</i>	
Talabalarning ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda kooperativ ta'limning metodik yondashuvlari.....	135
<i>Botiraliyeva Gulobar Mahamadismoil qizi</i>	
Talabalarni intellektual faoliyatga tayyorlashda ijtimoiy sherikchilikning pedagogik va metodik asoslari	139
<i>Dilbarjonov Avazbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
Teacher-Centered and Child-Centered Methods in Early Childhood Education: Insights From Finland and Uzbekistan	143
<i>Djaparova Gulnoza</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida "Metodik mahorat kuni" va "Metodik mahorat soati"ni tashkil etish	150
<i>Do'stov Davron Zulhaydarovich</i>	
Theoretical, Methodological, and Practical Factors of Differentiated Education	155
<i>Ergash Shonazarovich Khasanov</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda kognitiv yondoshuv	160
<i>Gulbahor Xamidova</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim – mustahkam bilim.....	164
<i>Halima Shukurova Sunatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Google Classroom and Project-Based Learning for Enhanced Synchronous and Asynchronous Education.....	168
<i>Inomkhojaeva Shodiyakhon Abdukodirkhoja qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion fikrlash ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	174
<i>Mamadaliyev Axadjon G'aniboyevich</i>	
Hududiy rivojlanishda innovatsion yondashuvlarni strategik boshqaruvga integratsiya qilish yo'llari.....	177
<i>Mo'minov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li</i>	
O'rta yoshdagi ayollarda harakat faoliyatini rivojlantirishda milliy o'yinlarning pedagogik ahamiyati	184
<i>Mustafoev Sherali</i>	
Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of Developing Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Students.....	188
<i>Nasimova Zarina Isomiddin kizi</i>	
Pedagogik ijodkorlikning kasbiy professionallikda namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari.....	193
<i>Numonova Dildor Umurzoqovna</i>	
Ko'zi oqiz boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini o'rganishning nazariy asoslari	196
<i>Qarshiboyev Asliddin</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etish masalalari.....	200
<i>Qilichova Marxabo Xudayqulovna</i>	
The Transformation of Existential Thought in British Literature: Iris Murdoch's Philosophical Humanism and the Reinterpretation of Freedom	204
<i>Rahmonqulova Zarnigor Nasimjon qizi</i>	
Sportchilarning elektron platformalardan foydalanishning metodik tahlili	209
<i>Saydullayev Zafar Erkinovich</i>	
Adabiy ta'limda estetik tarbiya	216
<i>Sharipov Elmurod Sa'dulla o'g'li</i>	
O'qituvchi-trenerning ko'p qirrali kasbiy-pedagogik funksiyalari	220
<i>Sulaymonov Jaxongir Solijonovich</i>	
Uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishda art-pedagogikaning o'qituvchilar hissiy farovonligiga ta'siri	223
<i>Suvanova Kamola Raimqul qizi</i>	

Raqamlashtirish muhitida umumta'lim maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish	226
<i>Xamidova Komila Maxmudovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda kvest texnologiyasi yordamida fizika fanining murakkab tushunchalarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi.....	231
<i>Yo'ichiyev Shaxriyor Xusanovich, O'rinboyeva Kumushoy Sultonbek qizi</i>	
Совершенствование профессиональных компетенций будущих инженеров на основе интегративного подхода	235
<i>Умарова Гулчехра Абитовна</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning aqliy qobiliyatining psixologik xususiyatlari	238
<i>Alanazarova Sholpan Artikbaevna, Artiqbaeva Miyassar Jumanazarovna</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida innovatsion metodlarni joriy etishda ta'lim menejmentining roli.....	241
<i>Allayorova Maloxat Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Integrating Innovative Technologies for the Enhancement of Speech and Communication Skills Among Learners With Intellectual Disabilities in Uzbekistan: Pedagogical Approaches and Developmental Outcomes	244
<i>Donisheva Gulruy Akhrorkulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini o'quvchilar o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishga metodik jihatdan tayyorlash.....	247
<i>Doniyarov Mavlonbek Arabovich</i>	
Kimyoviy birikmalarda bog'lar sonini hisoblashning yangi matematik usullari.....	252
<i>Ergashev Vahob Ergashevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	257
<i>G'aniyeva Maftuna Abduaziz qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida steam fanlarini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida o'qitishning metodik asoslari	261
<i>Jamolova Sitora Muzaffar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining matematik tafakkurini rivojlantirishda didaktik o'yinlar va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish samaradorligi	264
<i>Mamadiyurov Jamol</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalar mustaqil faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik yondashuvlar.....	268
<i>Mamayusupova Nafisa Abdulatifovna</i>	
Para yengil atletikachilarda nayza uloqtirish texnikasini takomillashtirish uslubiyati	271
<i>Qiyomova Shohsanam Yarash qizi</i>	
Difficulties in Enhancing Communicativeness of Pre-Service English Teachers.....	275
<i>Kurbonova Maftuna Fakhriddinovna, Mirzayeva Gulshan Azamatovna</i>	
Principles of Teaching Basic Foreign Language Skills (EFL)	278
<i>Samandarova Gulsara Ismatilloevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion ta'lim muhitida tayanch kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning dolzarbligi	282
<i>Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna</i>	
Корпоративная культура педагогов и внутренняя стабильность ДОО	286
<i>Буранова Шохноза Абдуразаковна</i>	
Развивать личностные качества учащихся на уроках географии.....	290
<i>Шадиева Нигора Шариповна</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida oliy ta'lim sifatini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar	295
<i>Baytileuova Gulnaz Quralbay qizi</i>	
Yangi avlod pedagoglarini tayyorlash: kompetensiyalar va qadriyatlarining roli.....	298
<i>Ro'ziboyeva Ma'mura Abdunabiyevna</i>	
Astronomiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanib o'qitishning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni	301
<i>Barakayeva Sarvinov To'iqunovna</i>	
Alohida e'tiborga muhtoj bolalar bilan ishlashda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash.....	305
<i>Usmonov Salohiddin Dushan o'g'li, Namozova Sevinch Asqar qizi</i>	
Ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarni tarbiyalashda pedagogik qadriyatlarining ustuvorligi.....	310
<i>Jumayeva Gulnara Tursunpulatovna</i>	
Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini maqsadli boshqarishga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari	314
<i>Mahmudova Zulfiya Xomitovna</i>	
Pedagogical Methodology Improve Students' Professional Mobility in Acquisition of Specialty.....	319
<i>Khidirova Muhabbat Murodillayevna</i>	

INTEGRATING GOOGLE CLASSROOM AND PROJECT-BASED LEARNING FOR ENHANCED SYNCHRONOUS AND ASYNCHRONOUS EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the use of Google Classroom in education and its potential to combine synchronous (real-time) and asynchronous (self-paced) learning. Particular attention is given to the integration of Project-Based Learning (PBL) with Google Classroom, highlighting its effectiveness, benefits, and challenges. The findings suggest that the hybrid learning model reduces rigidity, fosters student engagement, motivation, and achievement, and proves especially effective in English as a Second Language (ESL) education.

Key words: Google Classroom, Project-Based Learning (PBL), synchronous learning, asynchronous learning, ESL education, student engagement, online learning, digital tools, hybrid learning, collaborative learning, reflective practices, educational technology, digital literacy, learning outcomes, student motivation, virtual classroom, interactive learning, real-time communication, flexible learning environment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Google Classroom platformasining ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishi, uning sinxron (real vaqt rejimida) va asinxron (mustaqil o'quvchi tezligida) ta'limni birlashtirishdagi imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, loyihaviy yondashuv (Project-Based Learning – PBL) bilan uyg'unlashtirilgan holda Google Classroom'ning samaradorligi, afzalliklari va mavjud muammolari o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, gibrid ta'lim modeli qat'iylikni yumshatib, talabalarning faolligi, motivatsiyasi va o'zlashtirish darajasini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, ingliz tili ikkinchi til sifatida o'qitiladigan yo'nalishlarda mazkur integratsiya samarali natijalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Google Classroom, Project-Based Learning (PBL), sinxron ta'lim, asinxron ta'lim, ESL ta'limi, talaba faolligi, onlayn ta'lim, raqamli vositalar, gibrid ta'lim, hamkorlikdagi ta'lim, reflektiv amaliyotlar, ta'lim texnologiyalari, raqamli savodxonlik, o'quv natijalari, talaba motivatsiyasi, virtual sinf, interaktiv ta'lim, real vaqt kommunikatsiyasi, moslashuvchan ta'lim muhiti.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается использование платформы Google Classroom в образовательном процессе, а также её роль в сочетании синхронного (в реальном времени) и асинхронного (в индивидуальном темпе) обучения. Особое внимание уделяется эффективности интеграции с проектно-ориентированным обучением (Project-Based Learning – PBL), её преимуществам и вызовам. Результаты исследования показывают, что гибридная модель обучения способствует снижению чрезмерной строгости, повышает активность студентов, их мотивацию и академическую успеваемость. Особенно эффективным данный подход является в преподавании английского языка как второго (ESL).

Ключевые слова: Google Classroom, Project-Based Learning (PBL), синхронное обучение, асинхронное обучение, ESL образование, вовлечённость студентов, онлайн обучение, цифровые инструменты, гибридное обучение, совместное обучение, рефлексивные практики, образовательные технологии, цифровая грамотность, учебные результаты, мотивация студентов, виртуальный класс, интерактивное обучение, коммуникация в реальном времени, гибкая образовательная среда.

INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic urgently required the transition to online education, prompting educational institutions to support teaching and learning with digital tools. Of all these tools, Google Classroom has made its way to the must-have list, providing dual means to enable synchronous (real-time) along with asynchronous (self-paced) learning environments. Before we dive too deeply, one of the core concepts of our study is exposing how the integration of Google Classroom and Project-Based Learning (PBL) can better complement ESL public school education. However, combining these can, in fact, lead to more inclusive and efficient learning, because they can almost always reach different learning styles and paces. Online teaching

has brought the necessity of digital tools to light, and these tools must be adaptable to meet the demands of all types of learners. Google Classroom is a one-stop-shop solution for handling online coursework, facilitating live interactions, as well as ensuring a flexible learning space. At the same time, Project-Based Learning (PBL) encourages active learning by developing real-world problem-solving skills and projects requiring collaboration. If combined, more student engagement, greater motivation, and higher academic achievement are also likely to be seen, particularly in ESL education.

The purpose of this paper is to explore the implementation process, benefits, issues, and effectiveness of applying Google Classroom combined with PBL in the Skills for ESL course. This study specifically intends to:

1. Consider the impact of the bifurcated model on student engagement and motivation.
2. Identify how to implement Google Classroom integration with the PBL model.
3. Provide strategies for overcoming these challenges and making the most of the learning journey.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on integrating digital tools with Project-Based Learning (PBL) shows significant impact on student engagement and learning. Blumenfeld, Soloway, Marx, Krajcik, Guzdial, and Palincsar emphasized that PBL sustains motivation and supports deeper learning through authentic tasks. Kokotsaki, Menzies, and Wiggins highlighted that PBL improves collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity when properly scaffolded. Similarly, Burnett, Merchant, Pahl, and Rowsell demonstrated that digital literacy projects enhance classroom practice by encouraging active and interactive learning processes.

The role of Google Classroom as a digital platform has been analyzed in recent studies. Glazunova, Kudryashova, Ivanova, and Mukhacheva underlined its effectiveness in fostering engagement and participation in online learning environments. Friska reported that students perceived Google Classroom as a useful blended learning tool that supports communication and feedback. In ESL education, Han, Yalvac, Capraro, and Capraro showed that combining technology with project-based approaches helps develop language skills, collaboration, and problem-solving abilities. Together, these findings suggest that the integration of Google Classroom and PBL can offer a powerful model for inclusive and effective education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We used a mixed-methods design that included quantitative and qualitative data collection to conduct the research. The study used a PBL project from the pilot project work of ESL Level 2 students at Westminster International University in Tashkent (WIUT). A total of 81 ESL Level 2 students from WIUT took part in the study. They were divided into 4–5 member groups and participated in two PBL projects (as opposed to one full-size PBL, based at the school campus) targeting:

- 1) an outdoor project promoting a local site, and
- 2) an indoor dubbing project.

The data was collected through surveys, interviews, reflective journals, and research diaries in order to obtain both quantitative and qualitative information. Student participation, engagement, perceived challenge, and interest were measured using surveys. The interviews and reflective journals provided further details and constructs to the quantitative data, illustrating the qualitative experiences perceived by students. Questions asked in the survey referred to participation rates, engagement levels, difficulty of projects, and interest levels. The students rated their experiences using a Likert scale to quantitatively measure their engagement and learning outcomes. Open-ended questions further encouraged students to share their ideas and opinions in their own words.

During the project, students kept reflective journals to document experiences, problems encountered, and learning outcomes. These journals allowed the capture of qualitative data that added another layer of understanding to the survey results, helping develop a more holistic view of student engagement and the development of 21st-century skills. A number of students and teachers were invited for semi-structured interviews to reflect on their experiences of Google Classroom usage in the context of PBL integration. These interviews allowed us to gather information on the hybrid model and provided insights into some of its challenges and benefits, as well as possible ways to implement the hybrid model successfully.

ANALYS AND RESULTS

Participation, difficulty, interest, and learning outcome sections of the study are presented along with the findings of this research. Each section presents quantitative data along with qualitative reflections from interviews and reflective journals.

A large number of students participated in the projects, with a participation rate of 98.77%. The engagement index also had a high score (78.3), again indicating strong student engagement. Certainly, this was an improvement since 93.8% of students thought it helped them learn English, and 91.4% would welcome more projects in the future.

Figure 1: Participation Reflection Chart

Difficulty and Interest

The difficulty perception index was 54.325, reflecting a moderate level of challenge. The interest level was 47.25, suggesting that students found the projects fairly engaging. The dubbing project was considered more interesting by 54.3% of the respondents, while 44.4% preferred the advertising project.

Learning Outcomes

The effectiveness of learning outcomes was high, with 94.4% of students reporting significant improvement in vocabulary, teamwork, communication, creative thinking, and self-confidence. Reflective practices and feedback sessions contributed to these outcomes by enabling continuous improvement and self-assessment.

Figure 2: Project Interest Chart

Calculations

The following calculations provide a quantitative assessment of the project effectiveness:

- **Participation Rate:**

Participation Rate = $(8081) \times 100 = 98.77\%$
 $\text{Participation Rate} = \left(\frac{80}{81} \right) \times 100 = 98.77\%$

- **Engagement Index:**

Engagement Index = $(0.9 \times 45.7) + (0.75 \times 42) + (0.5 \times 11.1) + (0.1 \times 1.2) = 41.13 + 31.5 + 5.55 + 0.12 = 78.3$
 $\text{Engagement Index} = (0.9 \times 45.7) + (0.75 \times 42) + (0.5 \times 11.1) + (0.1 \times 1.2) = 41.13 + 31.5 + 5.55 + 0.12 = 78.3$

- **Difficulty Perception Index:**

Difficulty Index = $(0.1 \times 18.5) + (0.5 \times 34.6) + (0.75 \times 46.9) = 1.85 + 17.3 + 35.175 = 54.325$
 $\text{Difficulty Index} = (0.1 \times 18.5) + (0.5 \times 34.6) + (0.75 \times 46.9) = 1.85 + 17.3 + 35.175 = 54.325$

- **Interest Level:**

Interest Level = $(0.5 \times 54.3) + (0.45 \times 44.4) + (0.1 \times 1.2) = 27.15 + 19.98 + 0.12 = 47.25$
 $\text{Interest Level} = (0.5 \times 54.3) + (0.45 \times 44.4) + (0.1 \times 1.2) = 27.15 + 19.98 + 0.12 = 47.25$

- **Learning Outcomes Effectiveness:**

Learning Outcomes Effectiveness = 94.4%
 $\text{Learning Outcomes Effectiveness} = 94.4\%$

These metrics provide a quantitative assessment of the project's effectiveness, indicating high participation and engagement, moderate difficulty, significant interest, and substantial learning outcomes.

Combining Google Classroom and PBL creates a balanced ecosystem for learning – controlled yet collaborative, stable yet exploratory. Real-time communication and active participation are promoted by synchronous activities such as discussions and feedback sessions hosted live. By embedding asynchronous activities – collaborative document editing, video presentations – students study at their own pace and can revisit the contents as many times as they like. This hybrid model allows flexibility of learning styles and working schedules, ensuring that ongoing project work, peer collaboration, and reflection are consistently taking place, which is key to PBL.

The following features of Google Classroom allow for both synchronous and asynchronous learning. Integrating it with other Google Workspace tools such as Google Docs, Slides, Sheets, and Forms increases interactions with students and boosts collaborative learning. In addition, Google Classroom enables the use of multimedia material, allowing educators to create multimedia-enhanced, engaging, and interactive educational experiences (Glazunova et al., 2023).

PBL, on the other hand, promotes active learning with problem-solving and collaboration on projects. Through the integration of PBL with Google Classroom, educators can combine the best of both worlds to provide a learning experience that is both inclusive and effective. The hybrid model motivates students to delve into the content, promotes critical thinking, and enables them to apply knowledge in practice (Kokotsaki, Menzies, & Wiggins, 2016).

While there are many benefits, utilizing both Google Classroom and PBL can be challenging due to technological limitations and different levels of digital literacy. Addressing these problems requires providing consistent internet access, distributing devices to those in need, and organizing digital upskilling sessions. Furthermore, the use of multimedia materials with built-in interactive exercises enables more active participation and raises the interest and motivation of students studying online.

Low access to reliable internet and digital hardware can slow the reach of online teaching. To address this, educational institutions should invest in improving internet infrastructure and provide necessary devices to students. In addition, partnerships with technology companies can allow low- or no-cost access to digital tools and services (Hipitronic, Sharma, & Novak, 2022).

Digital literacy among students and faculty may also present challenges, as efficient use of online tools requires adequate training. Training sessions on digital platforms can help fill this gap. User-friendly tutorials and resources, provided for both students and teachers, can offer guidance for navigating these platforms (Friska, 2021).

There are limited opportunities to engage young learners, especially in asynchronous environments. Multi-media content – videos, interactive quizzes, and discussion forums – can improve engagement. The use of gamification elements such as scores, badges, and leaderboards may further stimulate active involvement of students (Dicheva et al., 2015).

IMPLEMENTATION

In order to take full advantage of Google Classroom and Project-Based Learning, educators should consider the following strategies.

By structuring courses with clear purpose and timeline, students better understand expectations and tasks. In addition to organizing course materials, assignments, and feedback, using Google Classroom synchronizes the learning process (Glazunova et al., 2023). The key to student growth is consistent and effective feedback. With Google Classroom, teachers can return assignments and participate in real-time discussions during synchronous sessions. This ongoing feedback and encouragement help students refine their work and maintain motivation (Hattie & Timperley, 2007).

Promoting collaborative learning through group projects and peer reviews can also increase engagement and outcomes. Google Classroom supports online collaboration processes, allowing students to co-edit presentations, consult each other, and provide feedback (Johnson & Johnson, 1989). As Eisner (1985) suggested, promoting reflective practices helps students to become self-aware and improve critical thinking skills. The use of digital reflective journals, discussion threads, or multimedia presentations through Google Classroom stimulates reflective practices and deeper learning (Hidi & Renninger, 2006).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study demonstrates that integrating Google Classroom with Project-Based Learning (PBL) fosters higher student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, particularly in ESL education. The hybrid approach balances synchronous and asynchronous modes, ensuring flexibility, collaboration, and reflective learning.

Recommendations:

1. Institutions should enhance digital infrastructure and provide access to devices for equitable learning opportunities.
2. Teachers should employ a hybrid model that combines real-time feedback with self-paced tasks.
3. Training programs on digital literacy should be organized for both educators and students.
4. Greater use of multimedia and interactive tools is advised to boost motivation and critical thinking.
5. Continuous feedback and reflective practices should be embedded into project work to strengthen outcomes.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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